

THE PREMIS OF METADATA IN SIPs: PRODUCER VERSUS SYSTEM-GENERATED PRESERVATION METADATA

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Abstract - This paper examines the implementation of the PREMIS Data Dictionary for Preservation Metadata in the context of a pilot project aimed at developing a shared digital preservation solution for multiple Government cultural institutions in New South Wales, Australia. It provides a case study exploring the challenges and decisions made in the creation of a Common Submission Information Package (SIP) Specification, particularly regarding the creation and use of preservation metadata by Producers versus digital preservation systems. It highlights the need for guidance on implementing PREMIS in SIPs and suggests potential areas for further documentation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

PREMIS version 3.0 was implemented as part of a pilot project evaluating a scalable, shared solution for digital preservation across multiple Government cultural institutions in New South Wales (NSW), Australia. The overall solution design was informed by more than 150 prioritised requirements developed through stakeholder consultation. Beyond a digital preservation system, the *Digitisation and ICT Infrastructure for Cultural Sector Preservation and Access* project (the project) included storage infrastructure, application programming interfaces, and a web application for managing Submission

Information Packages (SIPs) adhering to a project specification.

A logically separate repository was created for each institution to ingest and manage their own sample digital collections, representative of their overall collection holdings. The State Library of NSW (the Library) was the only institution involved in the project with a digital preservation system in place, addressing the challenge of system migration between the production system and project system.

The PREMIS Data Dictionary is an important resource for implementing preservation metadata in digital preservation systems. Guidance and suggested practices are provided [1], [2]; however, its use as part of workflows prior to ingestion into a digital preservation system are not as clearly defined.

Submission Information Package is a term from the reference model for Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS), used to describe an Information Package delivered by a Producer to a digital preservation system [3]. In practice, PREMIS metadata is supplied in SIPs by digital preservation practitioners and used in the construction of Archival Information Packages (AIPs) by digital preservation systems. The implementation and conformance of PREMIS within digital preservation systems is managed by vendors. This paper refers to Producers as the creators of SIPs, not creators of Content Data Objects.

With no distinction in the Data Dictionary between PREMIS semantic units that can be used in SIPs and those that should be reserved for use by systems, assumptions and decisions were made in the development of a SIP specification as part of the project. This raised questions on what preservation metadata should be generated and supplied by Producers versus those that should be generated by digital preservation systems on ingest.

A. Related Work and Context

The PREMIS Data Dictionary was designed to be flexible, where context dictates its implementation. Resources exist with practical guidance examples that highlight considerations in specifying digital preservation metadata profiles [4]. PREMIS is commonly mentioned in the context of SIPs. There are software applications for SIP creation and SIP specifications that incorporate PREMIS, such as E-ARK Common Specification for Information Packages [5], docuteam packer [6], and Pre-ingest Tool [7]. Implementation case studies have been published that discuss the use of PREMIS in SIPs [8], [9].

However, SIPs are only mentioned three times in the PREMIS Data Dictionary, twice under originalName [1, p. 86] and once in the glossary under the term Ingest [1, p. 270]. The project team did not find any guidance on implementing PREMIS in SIPs during the research phase of the project, or in writing this paper.

The “PREMIS Digital Preservation Metadata Birds of a Feather” session at iPRES 2024 included discussion on the community’s needs as users,

where participants identified a need for examples of implementation in different contexts. This paper provides an opportunity to identify any existing resources that may have been missed by the project team and highlight a potential gap in PREMIS documentation and guidance relating to its use in SIPs.

II. A COMMON SUBMISSION INFORMATION PACKAGE

The Common SIP Specification [10] (the Specification) was developed for the project to abstract from vendor or system-specific SIP requirements and simplify future system migration. It also aimed to support cross-domain collaboration between cultural institutions and allow SIP preparation to begin prior to procurement of a digital preservation system.

The Specification incorporates established standards including OAIS and PREMIS, with the intention to reach a compromise between ease of SIP creation, both manually and automated, and support the diverse metadata requirements and digital materials from a library, gallery, museum, and performing arts centre. It was developed to allow SIPs to be as simple or as complex as required, with a minimal set of mandatory metadata requirements.

The Common SIP structure is based on the BagIt File Packaging Format version 0.97 [11], with the payload including metadata files and Representation directories as seen in Fig. 1. The SIP or bag name is based on a code for each institution plus a unique identifier for that SIP.

Figure 1: Common SIP Specification structure, where (M) indicates mandatory elements.

Metadata is provided in the XML-based Excel Workbook (.xlsx) file format and can contain up to twenty-two sheets with extensive PREMIS metadata. The Specification covers PREMIS concepts of Intellectual Entity, Representation and File in addition to preservation metadata including Events, Agents and Rights statements.

B. Assumptions and Decisions

The Specification was developed with the assumption that Common SIPs would be transformed to meet the SIP requirements of the digital preservation system selected for the project, with a separate instance for each institution. Following procurement, the vendor committed to implementing the Common SIP Specification as a submission format for conversion to an AIP, in addition to the PREMIS version 3.0 Data Dictionary. This removed the constraint of a proprietary SIP format that may not have supported all PREMIS semantic units in the Specification. If not supported in SIPs for the chosen system, some or all PREMIS metadata would likely have been stored in an XML file within an Intellectual Entity.

The use of the PREMIS Data Model and Data Dictionary requires adaption and selection on semantic units [8, p. 279]. With minimal guidance on system-reserved semantic units, the Specification only includes those that the project team considered functional in the context of a SIP. This evolved over time with use and implementation in the digital preservation system.

In addition to those outlined further in this paper, the following decisions were made for implementing PREMIS in the Specification:

- Environment Objects are not supported. This complex modelling is handled differently (if at all) in digital preservation systems and is too difficult to generalise into a common SIP specification.
- The Object subcategory Bitstream is not supported. This is unlikely to be used in a SIP and semantic units at this level should be generated automatically by the system.
- 1.5.2 Fixity metadata is provided in the BagIt payload manifest, which is validated and stored as part of SIP ingest within the system.

- Object Characteristics 1.5.3 Size and 1.5.4 Format are typically determined by digital preservation systems and are not included in the Specification.
- In some cases, the controlled vocabularies provided in the Data Dictionary are documented as recommendations in the Specification.
- Non-digital representations are not supported as physical representations were not a requirement of the project.

Each cultural institution was responsible for defining their own data model, including their own Object subcategories, within the limitations of the Specification. While the Specification supports broad PREMIS metadata, there was also an expectation that the digital preservation system would include tools to extract and store technical metadata as part of the ingest process.

III. CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

The PREMIS Data Dictionary outlines data constraints, repeatability, and obligation in addition to usage notes for each semantic unit. Developing the Specification required technical expertise and a deep understanding of PREMIS, with several challenges encountered and resolved during the project.

C. Object Identifiers and Relationships

The Specification includes PREMIS Objects, Events, Agents and Rights Statements and supports a subset of the relationships between these Entities [12]. The correct usage of Entity identifiers and defining relationships between Entities in the context of SIPs was not clear.

For example, we needed a method to record a pre-ingest Event for a specific file within a SIP. The first idea was to follow the Data Dictionary closely and mandate that a File identifier must be supplied for each File object in the SIP. The SIP creator would then use this File identifier to define the relationship between Event and File within the SIP. According to the Creation / Maintenance Notes for container 1.1 objectIdentifier, "An identifier may be created by the repository system at the time of ingest, or it may be created or assigned outside of the repository and submitted with an object as metadata. Similarly, identifiers can be generated automatically or

manually" [1, p. 37]. This looks promising; however, it is also states that an Object identifier is "a designation used to identify the Object uniquely within the preservation repository system in which it is stored" [1, p. 37]. This raises a problem; how do we ensure the Object identifier is not already used within the digital preservation system? We could build these checks in our code for automated ingestion workflows, but for manual workflows our SIP creators would have to manually check the digital preservation system. Alternatively, we could have used Universally Unique Identifiers. Both options would be onerous for Producers creating SIPs manually.

We then encounter the next problem; the selected digital preservation system generates its own PREMIS Object identifiers during ingestion. PREMIS refers to primary and secondary Identifiers, where the requirement for identifiers to be unique only applies to primary [1, p. 36]. Therefore, we could generate an Object identifier that is unique only within the limited scope of a SIP and use this as a secondary Identifier. This method avoids the requirement to uniquely identify the Object across the entire repository. This could work if the digital preservation system understood these secondary identifiers as unique within the context of the SIP, creating the actual PREMIS link between the Event and File within the system using the primary identifier it generates for the File.

However, this approach would add work for SIP creators and the system vendor. Ultimately, we decided to use a file path to identify the file within the SIP metadata. In the Specification, the sheet PREMIS_Files_events has a row for recording each File level Event. This sheet contains a file_path column that is used to refer to the File the Event applies to. The digital preservation system processes this on ingest and determines that this Event applies to the File Object for the file found at file_path. The responsibility for creating the identifier for the File Object is left to the digital preservation system.

Using the file_path in this way as a stand-in for the File Identifier within the SIP saves SIP creators from generating a File Identifier and entering a row with this Identifier for every file in the SIP. Additionally, file_path references the file on disk storage, so it is clear to any human or code looking at the PREMIS_Files_events worksheet. We use the file_path column as both a stand-in for PREMIS

Identifier and as a way of referencing the file on disk throughout the Specification.

For some other relationship types we opted for an implicit definition based on the file system structure. For example, to indicate that a File belongs to a Representation the SIP must contain a directory for the Representation. All files within a directory are implicitly part of that Representation. The digital preservation system makes the relationship explicit using the Object identifiers generated during ingestion.

D. Agents in SIPs

Agent information is supported for Events in PREMIS. The definition for container 3.1 agentIdentifier is "the designation used to uniquely identify the Agent within a preservation repository system" [1, p. 160]. The rationale further states "each Agent associated with the preservation repository must have a unique identifier to allow it to be related to Events and Rights statements" [1, p. 160]. PREMIS Agents take many forms, and we provide metadata in the SIPs to define and describe the Agents. Unlike a File that will generally only be referenced in a single SIP, the same Agent may be applied in many SIPs. Consider a person as an Agent, where that person works at an institution for many years and may be involved in thousands of pre-ingest events recorded in hundreds of SIPs. We do not want that person represented hundreds of times, with hundreds of different identifiers, in the system. For this reason, we decided not to generate a new identifier for the same Agent in each SIP as we did not want duplicate Agents in the digital preservation system.

We addressed this challenge by placing the onus on the SIP creator to consistently use Agent identifiers across their institutional SIPs. It is the responsibility of each institution to either maintain a controlled vocabulary of Agent Identifiers, use an existing controlled vocabulary, or enforce a convention. The Specification provides an example for identifiers of people Agents using the convention of firstname initial followed by surname, for example pbrotherton or mburgess.

As the Specification allows for Agent metadata in addition to the Agent Identifier, the Specification supplement advises that "ideally the DP system uses the Agent identifier to avoid duplication when the same Agent is used in multiple SIPs. It is therefore particularly important that you do not provide

varying data for Agents in different SIPs which have the same Agent Identifier as the DP system may discard everything aside from the Identifier.” [12]

Ultimately, the digital preservation system selected for the project did not maintain a database of PREMIS Agents, with Agent identifiers and other Agent information stored inline with the Event metadata. Nevertheless, enforcing consistency with Agent identifiers and metadata across all SIPs allows system users to search, group, and report on specific Agent Events accurately. It is worth noting that if the digital preservation system maintained an Agents database and generated its own Agent Identifiers, we would have considered using these Agent Identifiers in SIPs.

Another challenge with Agents in SIPs was how to handle different versions of the same software Agent. Semantic unit 3.4 agentVersion is defined as “the version of the Agent referenced in agentName, if agentType is software or hardware” [1, p. 165]. According to PREMIS you can link from an Event to an Agent using the semantic unit 2.6.2 linkingAgentIdentifierValue [1, p. 153]. Therefore, it follows that we need to have a unique Agent identifier value for each version of the Agent to unambiguously identify them.

The Specification states that the Agent identifier value “must uniquely identify a single agent in your repository. Note that this means should you wish to represent multiple versions of the same agent, the value here should include the version.” [10]. This is only applicable to software and hardware Agents and is necessary for SIP creators to manage their own meaningful Agent Identifiers.

For practical reasons, the Specification outlines a variation to Agent Identifiers: “PREMIS 3.0 technically allows duplicate Agent IDs across different Agent Identifier Type domains. The common SIP specification does not, each Agent ID must uniquely identify an agent across all Identifier Type domains. This is to make linking to Agents within the common SIP specification easier.” [12]

E. Limitations of Excel Workbook-based SIPs

One of the early decisions we made when designing our own SIP specification was how to provide the metadata. We considered several options including METS, our own XML schema, JSON, and CSV formats. For a fully automated solution, an XML based SIP was a logical choice, but the idea of

handcrafting nested XML structures was not appealing to SIP creators. The decision to use XML-based Excel Workbooks (XLSX) was based on the project requirement to support both manual and automated SIP creation.

The XLSX file format was chosen as a compromise that makes it easy for Producers to manually create SIPs and works sufficiently for automation. It has good support with Python [13], our chosen language for SIP processing, and utilising Workbooks with multiple worksheets provides some flexibility to represent the required PREMIS structures and relationships.

PREMIS semantic units are grouped into containers, which take no value of their own [1, p. 268]. Furthermore, semantic units can be nested, and we also needed to consider Repeatability and Obligation [1, p. 31]. Particularly where values for any of the optional or mandatory semantic units in a container is supplied and a value for all mandatory semantic units within the container must also be supplied [1, p. 268].

PREMIS attributes are relatively straightforward to represent in XML, however they pose challenges in the XLSX structure. For example, 2.5 eventOutcomeInformation is an optional, repeatable container that comprises the optional, non-repeatable 2.5.1 eventOutcome semantic unit. It also includes a repeatable container 2.5.2 eventOutcomeDetail, which comprises two semantic units [1, pp. 146-150].

We considered two options for representing the repeated data structures for 2.5 eventOutcomeInformation in a spreadsheet:

1. Utilise three separate worksheets: event, event outcome information, event outcome detail. This would use a column ID to reference between each worksheet.
2. Utilise one worksheet where semantic units are repeated columns that include sequential numbers. For example, eventOutcome1, eventOutcome2.

Our initial decision was to not support the repeatability of any semantic units. The Specification only supports a single 2.5 eventOutcomeInformation for each Event, but was updated to support repeated 2.4 eventDetailInformation to meet the requirements outlined in Section III-F.

We came across similar challenges with other PREMIS containers and Entities when designing our XLSX-based SIP specification. In each case we tried to strike a balance between supporting as many semantic units as possible, and simplicity for SIP creators, all the while keeping in mind that not all PREMIS semantic units make sense in the context of a SIP.

F. Documenting Pre-ingest Events

Recording events that occur prior to ingestion into a digital preservation system is a PREMIS implementation decision [1, p. 15]. It also relies on the support of digital preservation systems to accept them as part of a SIP. The State Library of NSW Digital Preservation Framework defines where pre-ingest preservation events are significant, they must be clearly documented and stored within the preservation system [14, p. 7]. The project provided an opportunity for the Library to re-evaluate the existing method for recording pre-ingest events, aligning with PREMIS version 3.0 rather than system-specific requirements for the production environment.

Changing the name of a born-digital file is considered a significant preservation action by the Library and other institutions [9]. Action may be undertaken pre-ingest to resolve issues with unsupported characters in filenames or missing or incorrect file extensions. There have been proposals to create new semantic units to support structured provenance notes [15]. One might also consider storing the original filename as a property of the PREMIS Object Entity, however this approach is not explicitly supported by the Data Dictionary.

1.6 originalName is defined as "the name of the object as submitted to or harvested by the repository, before any renaming by the repository". The rationale further elaborates that "this unit allows preservation systems to rename files but still retain the name of the object that was submitted" [1, p. 86]. While a repository is not defined in PREMIS as a system [1, p. 272], this semantic unit could be considered reserved for use by a digital preservation system to record filenames in SIPs and not used to record original filenames that have been changed as part of pre-ingest preservation workflows.

Ultimately, changing a filename pre-ingest is a preservation action and should therefore be recorded as an Event. The Library records pre-ingest

Events in an Excel Workbook in addition to a PREMIS Event in a SIP. The original filename was previously recorded in a single free text cell that described the action. For example, *Prohibited character removed. Filename changed from "this" to "that"*. Consequently, the previous filename was not stored in a separate metadata element that would enable automated processing in the future to reverse the preservation action if required.

An effective method for storing original filenames or filepaths separately was identified, utilising the repeatable 2.4 eventDetailInformation container with 2.4.1 eventDetail, as seen in Table 1. This method was influenced by the use of a custom 2.4.2 eventDetailExtension in the PREMIS metadata profile from the University of Texas [16]. Aiming to avoid the use of an extension schema, eventDetail was selected as it can be used to record any information about an Event [1, p. 86].

In addition to recording pre-ingest Events for filename changes, the Library also considered other significant Events. Hardware and software used to transfer born-digital collections from original physical digital carriers, and normalisation from Digital Original to Preservation Master representations pre-ingest, are also recorded as PREMIS Events to maintain provenance.

Table 1: Pre-ingest PREMIS Event for filename change

Workbook column	Value
event_type	filename change
event_date_time	2025-04-14 10:05:33
event_detail1	pre-ingest event
event_detail2	unsupported characters removed from filename
event_detail3	originalFilename:@photo#12.dng
event_outcome	success
linking_agent_identifier_value	mburgess
linking_agent_role	implementer
file_path	PRESERVATION_MASTER/photo12.dng

G. PREMIS Metadata Migration

The requirement for digital preservation systems to support pre-ingest Events is evident when considering migration. The Library was the only cultural institution involved in the project with a production environment system in place, where sample collections were migrated to the pilot platform. The source system used its own metadata schema based on PREMIS version 2 [17].

Regardless of the level of support for PREMIS metadata in the Specification, the decision was made to migrate the AIP METS XML file from the source system as part of Intellectual Entities. As with digital objects, changes to information packages should also be documented to provide the ability to reverse to a previous state [18, p. 14]. Handling the AIP from a source system as a digital object, similar to the treatment of information packages in other repositories [19], enables the comparison of metadata from the source to the destination system and provides a point-in-time snapshot of the Intellectual Entity before migration.

Decisions were still required on migration of Events from the source system as pre-ingest Events to the project platform. With technical metadata extraction occurring as part of ingestion, this information embedded within digital objects was not migrated from the source system. File format identification was considered critical, particularly where efforts had been made to correct misidentified or non-uniquely identified files.

IV. CONCLUSION

PREMIS is deliberately intended to be agnostic of any implementation or technology [20], and version 3.0 explicitly expands the scope beyond repository boundaries [1, p. 2], covering the whole lifecycle of digital objects beyond the scope of OAIS [21]. As outlined in this paper, implementing PREMIS requires decisions on the use of semantic units in the context of both SIPs and digital preservation systems. Without guidance on the use of semantic units in SIPs, implementation decisions were made as part of this project based on assumptions. Subsequently, the Specification evolved following use by digital preservation practitioners and more clearly defined PREMIS requirements from institutions as they prepared sample collections for ingestion.

This paper highlights an area where guidance is needed to support PREMIS implementation in SIPs and support good practice. This could be achieved by defining system-reserved semantic units in usage requirements within the Data Dictionary, although this may be at odds with its intention to be implementation agnostic [20]. Alternatively, guidelines for implementing PREMIS in SIPs could be developed, similar to other resources maintained by the PREMIS Editorial Committee [22], [23]. Lastly, the digital preservation community should continue to document and publish their PREMIS implementations for reference, as seen in [10], [16], and other examples cited in this paper.

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